

Densities, viscosities and excess thermodynamic properties of binary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar and non-polar solvents at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K

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Manuscript received 18 November 2008, revised 22 June 2009, accepted 26 June 2009

Abstract : Densities and viscosities of binary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar and non-polar solvents, viz. methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol, acetone, methyl ethyl ketone, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and toluene have been measured at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. From density and viscosity data the values of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and the thermodynamic excess properties viz. the excess molar volume (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) have been determined. The values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ have been fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomial equation to estimate the binary coefficients and standard deviation between the experimental and theoretical (calculated) values. From the small magnitude of the values of standard deviation it is concluded that the experimental values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ compare fairly well with the theoretical values predicted by Redlich-Kister equation. The effect of increasing temperature on the values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ as well as the nature of molecular interactions between the mixing components of the binaries has also been discussed.

Keywords : Densities, viscosities, excess thermodynamic properties, binary mixtures.

Introduction

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the viscosities of liquid mixtures because quantitative knowledge of this transport property is often required in chemical engineering design. Experimental transport property data are important because they have not been studied as much as other properties of liquid mixtures. The excess thermodynamic properties are useful in understanding the strength and the nature of interactions among the molecules of the binary liquid mixtures¹.

So far as the studies relating to the thermodynamic and transport properties of binary organic liquid mixtures of aliphatic amines with polar and non-polar solvents are concerned, a survey of literature reveals that Oswal and Patel²⁻⁴ have reported studies on viscosities and excess molar volumes for binary mixtures of triethylamine and tri-*n*-butylamine with *n*-hexane, *n*-octane, iso-octane, *n*-propyl amine, *n*-butyl amine, *n*-hexyl amine and *n*-octyl amine. Papaioannou *et al.*⁵ have measured the densities and viscosities of the binary mixtures of *n*-butyl amine with 1-alkanols (methanol, ethanol, 1-propanol and

1-butanol) at 25 °C. The results of the study reveal that all binary systems studied exhibit relatively large negative values of V^E . V^E is especially large (negative) in the mixture with methanol and decreases as the chain length of the alkanol increases. This is certainly indicative of the relative strength of the specific interactions between the hydroxyl and the amino groups in the above four mixtures. The large negative V^E for the mixture with methanol indicates that a most efficient packing of molecules occurs in this mixture. Aside from the strength of the OH---NH₂ interactions (compared to the strength of the OH---OH, NH₂---NH₂ interactions), this efficiency arises also from the relative sizes of the methanol and *n*-butyl amine molecules.

Ethylenediamine is a polar liquid and can form intermolecular hydrogen bond⁶. It is a base with dissociation constant, $K_b = 0.85 \times 10^{-4}$. From the survey of literature, it is seen that studies on the measurement of densities, viscosities and excess thermodynamic properties of binary liquid mixtures involving ethylenediamine and polar and non-polar solvents are still lacking. With this aim in

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view, comprehensive studies on the determination of densities, viscosities, viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and excess thermodynamic properties (V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$) of the following binary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar and non-polar solvents have been undertaken at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K : ethylenediamine + methyl alcohol; ethylenediamine + ethyl alcohol; ethylenediamine + *n*-propyl alcohol; ethylenediamine + *n*-butyl alcohol; ethylenediamine + acetone; ethylenediamine + methyl ethyl ketone; ethylenediamine + carbon tetrachloride; ethylenediamine + benzene and ethylenediamine + toluene.

Results and discussion

The densities (ρ) and viscosities (η) of binary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar and non-polar solvents, viz. methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol, acetone, methyl ethyl ketone (polar), carbon tetrachloride, benzene and toluene (non-polar) have been measured at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K as a function of the composition of the corresponding binary mixtures. The viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$), the excess molar volumes (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energy of activation of flow ($\Delta G^{#E}$) for binary mixtures have been determined using the well known equations^{5,7-9}. The representative data are presented in Table 1.

Correlation of experimental values of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$), the excess molar volume (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{#E}$) with the theoretical values :

The experimentally determined viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$), excess molar volumes (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{#E}$) for binary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar and non-polar solvents have been fitted to the Redlich-Kister's equation¹⁰.

$$Y_{ij}^E = x_i x_j \sum_{p=0}^P A_p (x_i - x_j)^p \quad (1)$$

where Y_{ij}^E is $\Delta\eta$ or V^E or $\Delta G^{#E}$, x_i denotes the mole fraction of component *i* of the *i, j* mixtures with $x_j = 1 - x_i$, and A_p are the adjustable parameters of Redlich-Kister's polynomial equation which were determined by the least squares method^{11,12} using a computer. The representative values of A_p along with the standard deviation (σ) are presented in Table 2. From the small magnitude of the values of σ , it is seen that the experimental values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$ compare fairly well with those calculated from Redlich-Kister equation.

Values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$ at different temperatures vis-à-vis molecular interactions :

The values of $\Delta\eta$, V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$ as a function of the composition of the binary liquid mixtures of ethylenedi-

Table 1. Densities (ρ), viscosities (η), viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and excess thermodynamic properties (V^E and $\Delta G^{#E}$) for the binary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar and non-polar solvents at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K

x_1	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	V (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)
Ethylenediamine + methyl alcohol						
Temp. 293.15 K						
0.0000	0.7898	0.5671	0.0000	40.567	0.0000	0.00
0.0629	0.8106	0.6647	0.0293	41.704	-0.5277	213.38
0.1313	0.8345	0.7615	0.0518	42.809	-1.2317	346.44
0.2061	0.8539	0.8583	0.0674	44.295	-1.7252	434.63
0.2876	0.8683	0.9624	0.0829	46.194	-1.9822	503.70
0.3770	0.8827	1.0705	0.0939	48.282	-2.2591	528.39
0.4758	0.8943	1.1821	0.0982	50.756	-2.3993	513.32
0.5852	0.9010	1.2975	0.0948	53.786	-2.2639	462.49
0.7078	0.9036	1.4141	0.0783	57.438	-1.8551	362.63
0.8447	0.9016	1.5326	0.0481	61.826	-1.0888	213.67
1.0000	0.8967	1.6532	0.0000	67.024	0.0000	0.00
Temp. 303.15 K						
0.0000	0.7824	0.5022	0.0000	40.951	0.0000	0.00
0.0629	0.8050	0.5706	0.0219	41.994	-0.6698	160.91
0.1313	0.8284	0.6405	0.0412	43.124	-1.4016	275.22

Table-1 (contd.)

0.2061	0.8485	0.7127	0.0581	44.577	-1.9862	361.16
0.2876	0.8637	0.7853	0.0705	46.440	-2.3420	418.24
0.3770	0.8756	0.8618	0.0809	48.674	-2.5424	452.14
0.4758	0.8859	0.9383	0.0843	51.237	-2.6690	443.54
0.5852	0.8897	1.0124	0.0776	54.469	-2.4163	399.14
0.7018	0.8920	1.0859	0.0604	58.185	-2.0383	304.94
0.8447	0.8886	1.1645	0.0378	62.731	-1.2201	182.49
1.0000	0.8815	1.2415	0.0000	68.179	0.0000	0.00
Temp. 313.15 K						
0.0000	0.7762	0.4272	0.0000	41.278	0.0000	0.00
0.0629	0.8021	0.4786	0.0102	42.146	-0.8435	114.94
0.1313	0.8275	0.5390	0.0259	43.171	-1.6786	231.41
0.2061	0.8458	0.5981	0.0360	44.719	-2.1660	314.50
0.2876	0.8612	0.6611	0.0457	46.575	-2.5273	376.59
0.3770	0.8749	0.7275	0.0536	48.713	-2.8214	408.59
0.4758	0.8853	0.7954	0.0569	51.272	-2.9500	405.07
0.5852	0.8880	0.8596	0.0495	54.573	-2.6250	360.86
0.7078	0.8902	0.9334	0.0431	58.303	-2.2306	289.35
0.8447	0.8864	1.0046	0.0247	62.886	-1.3713	166.27
1.0000	0.8776	1.0815	0.0000	68.482	0.0000	0.00
Ethylenediamine + acetone						
Temp. 293.15 K						
0.0000	0.7862	0.3115	0.0000	73.874	0.0000	0.00
0.1090	0.8373	0.6206	0.1629	69.629	-3.4988	1118.16
0.2158	0.8743	0.9214	0.3204	66.929	-5.4670	1575.87
0.3209	0.9144	1.2222	0.4801	64.226	-7.4499	1761.35
0.4237	0.9345	1.4920	0.6120	63.067	-7.9049	1809.30
0.5242	0.9502	1.6978	0.6830	62.238	-8.0447	1707.02
0.6233	0.9519	1.8618	0.7140	62.338	-7.2667	1556.01
0.7200	0.9375	1.9605	0.6830	63.503	-5.4383	1356.64
0.8150	0.9295	1.9580	0.5530	64.256	-4.0345	1018.34
0.9087	0.9146	1.8906	0.3599	65.510	-2.1389	621.12
1.0000	0.8967	1.6532	0.0000	67.024	0.0000	0.00
Temp. 303.15 K						
0.0000	0.7724	0.2872	0.0000	75.194	0.0000	0.00
0.1090	0.8298	0.5200	0.1288	70.258	-4.1715	949.84
0.2158	0.8724	0.7511	0.2580	67.075	-6.6058	1392.05
0.3209	0.9070	0.9674	0.3740	64.750	-8.1931	1579.16
0.4237	0.9322	1.1704	0.4789	63.222	-8.9996	1645.18
0.5242	0.9452	1.3083	0.5209	62.568	-8.9493	1553.67
0.6233	0.9466	1.4031	0.5211	62.687	-8.1353	1393.59
0.7200	0.9388	1.4623	0.4880	63.415	-6.7280	1193.98
0.8150	0.9293	1.4321	0.3671	64.270	-5.2068	848.06
0.9087	0.9085	1.3924	0.2380	65.950	-2.8697	519.65
1.0000	0.8815	1.2415	0.0000	68.179	0.0000	0.00
Temp. 313.15 K						
0.0000	0.7618	0.2525	0.0000	76.241	0.0000	0.00
0.1090	0.8268	0.4296	0.0867	70.513	-4.8818	797.94

Table-1 (contd.)

0.2158	0.8694	0.6064	0.1750	67.306	-7.2602	1199.51
0.3209	0.9063	0.7763	0.2578	64.800	-8.9509	1375.10
0.4237	0.9319	0.9417	0.3380	63.243	-9.7106	1454.02
0.5242	0.9442	1.0612	0.3741	62.634	-9.5397	1387.33
0.6233	0.9458	1.1362	0.3670	62.740	-8.6653	1221.87
0.7200	0.9338	1.1664	0.3170	63.755	-8.8995	992.76
0.8150	0.9289	1.1612	0.2331	64.298	-5.6196	669.95
0.9087	0.9065	1.1268	0.1210	66.096	-3.0950	334.75
1.0000	0.8776	1.0815	0.0000	68.482	0.0000	0.00

Ethylenediamine + carbon tetrachloride

Temp. 293.15 K

0.0000	1.5915	0.9621	0.0000	96.651	0.0000	0.00
0.1380	1.5275	1.0224	-0.0351	92.234	-0.3289	-24.82
0.2647	1.4628	1.0895	-0.0555	88.196	-0.6131	-33.13
0.3823	1.3952	1.1566	-0.0697	84.569	-0.7553	-40.04
0.4901	1.3270	1.2260	-0.0748	81.302	-0.8285	-40.09
0.5907	1.2573	1.2976	-0.0727	78.310	-0.8397	-36.11
0.6837	1.1866	1.3650	-0.0696	75.631	-0.7638	-37.27
0.7710	1.1152	1.4377	-0.0572	73.137	-0.6717	-29.84
0.8522	1.0427	1.5065	-0.0446	70.923	-0.4790	-25.49
0.9288	0.9691	1.5785	-0.0255	68.902	-0.2311	-14.91
1.0000	0.8967	1.6532	0.0000	67.024	0.0000	0.00

Temp. 303.15 K

0.0000	1.5772	0.8352	0.0000	97.527	0.0000	0.00
0.1380	1.5146	0.8586	-0.0327	93.019	-0.4583	-63.00
0.2647	1.4495	0.8814	-0.0613	89.005	-0.7542	-120.40
0.3823	1.3820	0.9158	-0.0747	85.377	-0.9306	-140.17
0.4901	1.3143	0.9547	-0.0796	82.088	-1.0561	-144.78
0.5907	1.2439	0.9963	-0.0789	79.154	-1.0375	-138.75
0.6837	1.1730	1.0379	-0.0751	76.508	-0.9542	-130.35
0.7710	1.1005	1.0838	-0.0647	74.114	-0.7864	-109.87
0.8522	1.0289	1.1352	-0.0462	71.875	-0.6422	-78.26
0.9288	0.9547	1.1867	-0.0259	69.941	-0.3276	-42.58
1.0000	0.8815	1.2415	0.0000	68.179	0.0000	0.00

Temp. 313.15 K

0.0000	1.5508	0.7332	0.0000	99.188	0.0000	0.00
0.1380	1.4934	0.7419	-0.0394	94.340	-0.6107	-106.31
0.2647	1.4310	0.7566	-0.0688	90.155	-0.9044	-179.36
0.3823	1.3667	0.7829	-0.0835	86.333	-1.1162	-208.79
0.4901	1.3011	0.8117	-0.0922	82.921	-1.2183	-224.84
0.5907	1.2336	0.8456	-0.0933	79.815	-1.2351	-222.48
0.6837	1.1643	0.8853	-0.0860	77.080	-1.1148	-198.24
0.7710	1.0936	0.9302	-0.0715	74.581	-0.9326	-159.37
0.8522	1.0228	0.9760	-0.0540	72.303	-0.7171	-118.85
0.9288	0.9505	1.0243	-0.0324	70.250	-0.4181	-71.73
1.0000	0.8776	1.0815	0.0000	68.482	0.0000	0.00

Ethylenediamine + benzene

Temp. 293.15 K

0.0000	0.8738	0.6441	0.0000	89.391	0.0000	0.00
0.1289	0.8814	0.6956	-0.0786	85.987	-0.5215	-112.83

Table-1 (contd.)

0.2498	0.8869	0.7600	-0.1362	82.998	-0.8055	-176.13
0.3639	0.8914	0.8221	-0.1892	80.274	-0.9777	-248.09
0.4708	0.8945	0.9008	-0.2184	77.843	-1.0171	-270.77
0.5716	0.8971	0.9914	-0.2295	75.594	-1.0117	-269.49
0.6669	0.8986	1.0962	-0.2209	73.558	-0.9163	-243.18
0.7565	0.8991	1.2124	-0.1951	71.722	-0.7478	-202.17
0.8420	0.8990	1.3442	-0.1496	70.017	-0.5403	-145.70
0.9230	0.8983	1.4906	-0.0849	68.448	-0.2979	-78.23
1.0000	0.8967	1.6532	0.0000	67.024	0.0000	0.00
Temp. 303.15 K						
0.0000	0.8576	0.5583	0.0000	91.080	0.0000	0.00
0.1289	0.8660	0.5589	-0.0875	87.516	-0.6123	-263.46
0.2498	0.8722	0.5648	-0.1642	84.397	-0.9622	-483.72
0.3639	0.8765	0.5992	-0.2077	81.639	-1.1078	-565.00
0.4708	0.8805	0.6444	-0.2356	79.081	-1.2171	-599.22
0.5716	0.8826	0.6981	-0.2507	76.836	-1.1538	-599.54
0.6669	0.8836	0.7730	-0.2409	74.807	-1.0008	-532.53
0.7565	0.8848	0.8681	-0.2070	72.881	-0.8741	-420.88
0.8420	0.8838	0.9683	-0.1653	71.222	-0.5760	-313.45
0.9230	0.8832	1.0936	-0.0953	69.618	-0.3243	-168.16
1.0000	0.8815	1.2415	0.0000	68.179	0.0000	0.00
Temp. 313.15 K						
0.0000	0.8351	0.4956	0.0000	93.534	0.0000	0.00
0.1289	0.8462	0.4704	-0.1007	89.563	-0.7412	-406.05
0.2498	0.8547	0.4651	-0.1769	86.125	-1.1507	-684.96
0.3639	0.8613	0.4778	-0.2310	83.079	-1.3382	-847.77
0.4708	0.8677	0.5047	-0.2667	80.248	-1.4918	-925.87
0.5716	0.8718	0.5445	-0.2860	17.788	-1.4264	-932.28
0.6669	0.8742	0.6133	-0.2730	75.611	-1.2159	-812.65
0.7565	0.8768	0.7067	-0.2321	73.546	-1.0359	-624.99
0.8420	0.8781	0.8050	-0.1839	71.684	-0.7565	-457.01
0.9230	0.8787	0.9259	-0.1105	69.975	-0.4365	-254.36
1.0000	0.8776	1.0815	0.0000	68.482	0.0000	0.00

Table 2. Coefficients of Redlich-Kister's equation and corresponding standard deviation (σ) for binary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar and non-polar solvents at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K

V^E	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	A_6	A_7	$\sigma (V^E)$
Ethylenediamine + methyl alcohol									
Temp. 293.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	0.392	-0.026	0.130	0.179	-1.100	-1.516	1.833	2.167	0.0003
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-9.617	0.865	6.242	-0.160	-35.138	0.705	46.596	8.543	0.0144
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	2014.0	-794.9	1046.8	336.5	-4564.0	-3954.7	7234.2	5744.7	1.8526
Temp. 303.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	0.336	-0.067	-0.185	-0.032	0.600	0.329	-0.554	-0.413	0.0004
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-10.590	2.420	9.387	2.256	-73.925	-50.487	111.732	94.371	0.0091
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	1748.9	-651.9	239.3	12.6	-1674.6	-1646.9	3533.5	3095.0	1.5924

Temp. 313.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	0.223	-0.099	-0.219	0.656	1 322	-0.976	-1 959	-0 191	0 0004
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-11.634	4.028	8.927	-17.355	-62 251	20.559	84 653	21 877	0 0124
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	1589.7	-665.8	147.7	1498 7	-37.4	-4276.7	-172 2	3627 1	1 1508
Ethylenediamine + acetone									
Temp. 293.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	2.683	1.168	0.539	3.438	-2.063	-10.959	2.840	10 403	0 0006
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-32.210	-1.451	-0.365	122.633	62.393	-459.119	-99 644	452.335	0 0032
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	6964.4	-2577.3	3267.5	8326.8	-705.6	-31852.2	2715.0	28821 6	1 0378
Temp. 303.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	2.060	0.468	-0.252	5.392	-0.039	-19.592	0 404	19 254	0.0013
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-36.216	4.536	8.224	15.129	-35.080	-73.336	22 723	81 164	0 0234
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	6340.2	-2571.9	1922.5	10396.0	-239.9	-41213.3	1673.7	39821.5	1.9519
Temp. 313 15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	1.483	0 506	-1.050	0.659	2.107	-3.536	-1.950	3.425	0 0013
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-38.841	4.417	10.201	61.735	-38.588	-261.196	10.251	274.049	0.0864
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	5663.0	-2047.7	-383.3	4802.7	4509.7	-22996.3	-4363.5	21979.0	0.3100
Ethylenediamine + carbon tetrachloride									
Temp. 293.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-0.297	-0.022	-0.118	-0.036	0.588	-0.379	-0.884	0.725	0.0011
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-3.346	-0.580	0.618	-0.494	-6.688	4.066	10.894	-6.978	0.0089
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-156.0	37.8	-194.2	-144.7	870.3	-365.5	-1291.0	1001.5	1.6816
Temp. 303.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-0.319	-0.014	-0.083	-0.383	-0.128	1.388	0.532	-1.596	0.00002
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-4.217	-1.133	1.467	6.348	-5.802	-21.283	3.878	19.323	0.0149
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-577.0	55.2	-170.7	-587.2	-355.5	2174.0	1321.2	-2817.3	0.5717
Temp. 313.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-0.370	-0.092	-0.023	0.288	-0.068	-0.459	0.130	-0.023	0.0001
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-4.905	-1.125	-0.658	5.632	5.012	-19.015	-11.022	20.458	0.0036
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-901.9	-136.9	-12.6	1124.8	-279.8	-2069.8	426.4	515.4	0.2445
Ethylenediamine + benzene									
Temp. 293.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-0.894	-0.280	-0.083	-0.151	0.681	-0.397	-1.152	1.075	0 0004
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-4.085	-0.088	-1.950	4.121	9.445	-15.491	-12 495	17 176	0.0022
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-1090.7	-22.8	-99.9	-318.0	2642 9	-1832.1	-4252.4	4107.9	1.1834
Temp. 303.15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-0.967	-0.416	-0.270	1.817	0.823	-5.773	-1.018	4.910	0.0007
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-4.870	1.140	4.786	-14.303	-29.220	63.720	37.535	-70.321	0.0138
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-2418.5	-305.9	-289.1	5621.0	1027.9	-16018.4	-656.0	12151 2	1.0093
Temp. 313 15 K									
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa.s)	-1.098	-0.514	-0.189	2.022	1.230	-6.277	-2.055	5 585	0.0005
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-5.993	0.721	6.667	-7.531	-34.271	39.805	39.134	-48 356	0.0099
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-3752.7	-631.1	530.2	8403.8	2913.2	-25002.4	-5959 8	21819.0	0.1834

amine with polar and non-polar solvents viz. methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol, acetone, methyl ethyl ketone, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and toluene at different temperatures have been determined. The representative data have been presented in Table 1. It is found that the values of $\Delta\eta$ for the binary mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar solvents are positive over the entire range of composition at different temperatures. The positive value of $\Delta\eta$ may be attributed to the presence of strong molecular interactions between the unlike molecules of the binary mixtures¹³. However, in the case of binary mixtures of ethylenediamine with non-polar solvents (carbon tetrachloride, benzene and toluene), the values of $\Delta\eta$ are negative. According to Fort and Moore⁷, negative values of $\Delta\eta$ occur for systems of different molecular sizes, and the dispersion forces are primarily responsible for the interactions. As in these mixtures the sizes of the molecules of mixing components differ appreciably it follows that the results of the present study are compatible with the views of Fort and Moore⁷.

The plots of $\Delta\eta$ versus x_1 (mole fraction of ethylenediamine) are of parabolic shape in each case and these are characterized by the presence of well-defined maxima in the case of binary mixtures of ethylenediamine with the polar solvents (Figs. 1–3), while with non-polar solvents well-defined minima are obtained (Fig. 4). These maxima/minima indicate the presence of complex formation between the mixing components^{14,15}.

The values of $\Delta\eta$ of all the binary mixtures decrease with the increasing temperature as revealed by the negative values of temperature coefficient of $\Delta\eta$, i.e.

$\left(\frac{\partial(\Delta\eta)}{\partial T}\right)_P$ (vide Table 3). From this it follows that with the rise of temperature the magnitude of $\Delta\eta$ decreases due to the rapid breaking up of hydrogen bonds in binary mixtures¹⁶.

The values of V^E have been found to be negative over the entire range of composition at different temperatures for all the binary mixtures under discussion. The negative values of V^E suggest¹⁷ the presence of specific molecular interactions occurring between the mixing components of the binary mixtures.

The plots of V^E versus x_1 are of parabolic shape in

Fig. 1. Variation of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) with mole fraction (x_1) of ethylenediamine in binary liquid mixture of ethylenediamine + methyl alcohol at different temperatures : (O) 293.15, (Δ) 303.15 and ($\square$) 313.15 K.

Fig. 2. Variation of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) with mole fraction (x_1) of ethylenediamine in binary liquid mixture of ethylenediamine + acetone at different temperatures : (O) 293.15, (Δ) 303.15 and ($\square$) 313.15 K.

Fig. 3. Variation of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) with mole fraction (x_1) of ethylenediamine in binary liquid mixture of ethylenediamine + methyl ethyl ketone at different temperatures : (O) 293.15, (Δ) 303.15 and ($\square$) 313.15 K.

Fig. 4. Variation of viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) with mole fraction (x_1) of ethylenediamine in binary liquid mixture of ethylenediamine + carbon tetrachloride at different temperatures : (O) 293.15, (Δ) 303.15 and ($\square$) 313.15 K.

Table 3. Values of $\left(\frac{\partial(\Delta\eta)}{\partial T}\right)_p$, $\left(\frac{\partial(V^E)}{\partial T}\right)_p$ and $\left(\frac{\partial(\Delta G^{\#E})}{\partial T}\right)_p$

for the binary liquid mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar and non-polar solvents at equimolar composition

Binary mixtures	$\left(\frac{\partial(\Delta\eta)}{\partial T}\right)_p$	$\left(\frac{\partial(V^E)}{\partial T}\right)_p$	$\left(\frac{\partial(\Delta G^{\#E})}{\partial T}\right)_p$
Ethylenediamine +			
Methyl alcohol	-0.0014	-0.0176	-4.1412
Ethyl alcohol	-0.0034	-0.0195	-3.8832
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	-0.0047	-0.0023	-3.7422
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	-0.0143	-0.0208	-5.6513
Acetone	-0.0104	-0.0608	-14.0481
Methyl ethyl ketone	-0.0007	-0.0470	-5.2152
Carbon tetrachloride	-0.0005	-0.0125	-5.4921
Benzene	-0.0016	-0.0125	-19.0879
Toluene	-0.0017	-0.0166	-18.4719

each case (Fig. 5) and are characterized by well-defined minima which indicate the presence of complex formation^{14,15}. With the rise of temperature the values of V^E

Fig. 5. Variation of excess molar volume (V^E) with mole fraction (x_1) of ethylenediamine in binary liquid mixture of ethylenediamine + methyl alcohol at different temperatures : (O) 293.15, (Δ) 303.15 and ($\square$) 313.15 K.

are rendered increasingly more negative. This is evidenced by the fact that the values of temperature coefficient of

v^E i.e. $\left(\frac{\partial(v^E)}{\partial T}\right)_P$ are negative (vide Table 3) for all the binary mixtures.^P

It is found that the values of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ are positive for the binary mixtures of ethylenediamine with polar solvents over the entire range of composition at different temperatures. However, the values are negative for the binary mixtures of ethylenediamine with non-polar solvents over the entire range of composition. The positive values of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ may be attributed to the presence of specific interactions¹⁸, while the negative values may be attributed to the presence of dispersion forces^{7,13} between the mixing components.

The plots of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ versus x_1 at different temperatures are of parabolic shape in each case and are characterized by the presence of well defined maxima/minima (Figs. 6 and 7). These give the composition at which the maximum interactions are expected between the mixing components of the binary liquid mixtures under discussion¹³.

Fig. 6. Variation of excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) with mole fraction (x_1) of ethylenediamine in binary liquid mixture of ethylenediamine + methyl alcohol at different temperatures : (O) 293.15, (Δ) 303.15 and ($\square$) 313.15 K.

Fig. 7. Variation of excess Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) with mole fraction (x_1) of ethylenediamine in binary liquid mixture of ethylenediamine + carbon tetrachloride at different temperatures : (O) 293.15, (Δ) 303.15 and ($\square$) 313.15 K.

It is also seen that the positive values of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ exhibit a decreasing trend with the rise of temperature in respect of the binary mixtures involving polar solvents, whereas in the case of binary mixtures involving non-polar solvents, the negative values of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ are rendered more negative with the rise in temperature. This is further supported by the fact that in both the cases the values of $\left(\frac{\partial(\Delta G^{\#E})}{\partial T}\right)_P$, are negative (vide Table 3).

Experimental

All the organic liquids used in the study were of analytical reagent grade. Ethylenediamine, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol, acetone, methyl ethyl ketone, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and toluene were obtained from Merck. The organic liquids were further purified for purity better than 99%, by the methods as reported in literature^{19,20}.

Liquid mixtures of various compositions were prepared by mass in a 25 cm³ flask using a Mettler analytical balance. The average uncertainty in the mole fraction of the mixtures was estimated to be less than ± 0.0001 . Density and viscosity measurements were carried out using a

thermostatically controlled, well-stirred water-bath to maintain temperature, which was measured with a digital thermometer with an uncertainty of ± 0.01 K.

Densities of pure liquids and their binary liquid mixtures were measured at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K with a digital vibrating tube densimeter (model 60/602, Anton parr, Austria). The densimeter was calibrated with degassed water and dehumidified air at atmospheric pressure.

The viscosities (η) of pure organic liquids and their binary mixtures were determined at different temperatures using an Ostwald viscometer. The details of the procedure have been reported in an earlier publication²¹. The uncertainty of calculated absolute viscosities was $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ mPa.s.

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